

Studies on the Interaction of Potassium Hexathiocyanatochromium(III) with Some Amines

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Three complexes, $K_3[Cr(SCN)_6A]$, $[Cr(SCN)_6B]$ and $K_3[Cr(NCS)_6C]$ where A = N-(2-aminoethyl) 1, 2-ethanediamine, B = N-(2-aminoethyl) 1, 3-propanediamine and C = deprotonated *trans* 1, 2-diaminocyclohexane-NNN'N' tetraacetic acid, have been prepared and characterised. The values of $10Dq$ are in the order: C > B > A. Thiocyanate coordinates through nitrogen in the third complex.

SEVERAL groups of workers¹⁻⁹ have reported their studies on the interaction of potassium hexathiocyanatochromium(III) with organic ligands in relation to their preparation, chemical analysis, ir, conductance and magnetic measurements. During the course of the reaction there was either a replacement of potassium ions with organic bases¹⁰⁻¹³ or of thiocyanate ions^{14, 15} forming the complexes of the type $Cr(NCS)_nL_{6-n}$ where L = aniline, acetamide, thiosemicarbazide, glycinate, alaninate, urea, thiourea, salicylate and ethylxanthate. The present communication deals with the preparation and characterisation of the interaction products of potassium hexathiocyanatochromium(III) and N-(2-aminoethyl) 1,3-propanediamine, N-(2-aminoethyl) 1,2-ethanediamine and *trans* 1, 2-diamino cyclohexane NNN'N' tetraacetic acid (DCTA).

Experimental

Materials and Methods :

All the reagents used were of AR, BDH grade and their solutions were prepared in double distilled water. The techniques, apparatus and methods of calculations used were the same as reported earlier¹⁶. The reflectance spectra were recorded on a Carl Zeiss SPEKOL spectrophotometer fitted with a reflectance attachment of the type Rd/O.

Preparation of the Complexes :

Potassium hexathiocyanatochromium(III) tetrahydrate was prepared in the laboratory by the method of Roesler¹⁷. The complexes given in Table 1 were prepared by mixing 0.1M solutions of the reactants i.e., $K_3[Cr(SCN)_6] \cdot 4H_2O$ and amine in the ratio of 1 : 1. The mixture was concentrated on water bath till shining green and violet crystals in the case of first and third complexes respectively and purple crystals of the second complex were formed. These were filtered and washings were carried out with distilled water in the case of complex nos. 2 and 3 while the crystals of first complex were washed with ethanol. The first and

third complex were soluble in water while the second in acetone.

Results and Discussion

The comparison of experimental absorption band energies (given in the first line) with the transition energies calculated on the basis of various numerical procedures can easily be made from the data given in Table 2, which also contain their deviation from the corresponding experimental values $\delta\nu = \nu_{calc} - \nu_{expt}$ (in reciprocal centimeters and in percent), the values of $10Dq$, B , $\beta_{3,3}$, ligand field stabilization energies, magnetic moments and molar conductances.

Using the equations suggested by Figgis, the splitting energy $10Dq$ can directly be derived from first spin allowed band (ν_1). The energies of ν_2 and ν_3 transitions have been evaluated using the standard equations which include configuration interactions¹⁹

$$E[{}^4T_{1g}(F) \leftarrow {}^4A_{2g}(F)] = 7.5B + 15Dq - \frac{1}{2} [(225B^2 + 100(Dq)^2 - 180DqB)^{1/2}]$$

$$E[{}^4T_{1g}(P) \leftarrow {}^4A_{2g}(F)] = 7.5B + 15Dq + \frac{1}{2} [225B^2 + 100(Dq)^2 - 180DqB]^{1/2}$$

The value of Racah's interelectronic repulsion parameter B has been calculated by three different methods as discussed by Konig¹⁹. The calculated values of B were then substituted in the energies equations to evaluate the extra band energy of ν_2 and ν_3 transitions.

Table 2 shows that the deviations $\delta\nu_{2,3}$ of the calculated transition energies according to procedures (a), (b) and (c) was of the order of a few percent and decreases according to $\delta\nu(b) > \delta\nu(a) > \delta\nu(c)$. Therefore, it was concluded that out of all the numerical procedures applicable in the spectra of the octahedral chromium(III) complexes, the best fit for the transitions ν_2 and ν_3 can be achieved by using the method (c), in which $\delta\nu_2$ and $\delta\nu_3$ are related as $|\delta\nu_2| = |\sigma\nu_3|$ i.e., the energies of

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TABLE 1—ANALYTICAL DATA OF THE COMPLEXES*

Sl. No.	Complexes**	Cr(%)	C(%)	H(%)	N(%)	Colour
1.	$K[Cr(SCN)_4(C_4H_{11}N_2)]$	11.84(12.20)	22.71(22.59)	3.40(2.05)	23.16(23.00)	Green
2.	$[Cr(SCN)_4(C_5H_{15}N_3)]$	14.92(15.16)	28.31(27.99)	4.05(4.37)	24.81(24.49)	Purple
3.	$K_2[Cr(NCS)_2(C_{14}H_{18}O_6N_4)]$	8.42(8.29)	30.22(30.62)	2.37(2.87)	9.06(8.93)	Violet

* The calculated values are in parentheses.

** $(C_4H_{11}N_2) = N-(2 \text{ aminoethyl})-1-2 \text{ ethanediamine}$

$(C_5H_{15}N_3) = N-2 \text{ (aminoethyl)-1-3 propanediamine}$

$(C_{14}H_{18}O_6N_4) = \text{deprotonated trans-1-2 diamine cyclohexane-N-N'-N'-N' tetraacetic acid.}$

TABLE 2—ELECTRONIC SPECTRAL DATA AND CALCULATED TRANSITION ENERGIES (in cm^{-1}) OF SPIN ALLOWED BANDS IN OCTAHEDRAL CHROMIUM(III) COMPLEXES

Complex	Method of calculation	Observed and calculated transition energies			B	$\beta_{s,s}$	$\delta\nu$ (cm^{-1})	$\delta\nu$ %	LFSE K cal/mole	μ_{eff} (B.M.)	Molar conductance
		${}^4A_{2g} \rightarrow {}^4T_{2g}$ (ν_1)	${}^4A_{2g} \rightarrow {}^4T_{1g}(F)$ (ν_2)	${}^4A_{2g} \rightarrow {}^4T_{1g}(P)$ (ν_3)							
$K[Cr(SCN)_4(C_4H_{11}N_2)]$	Expt.	17420	23800	37500	—	—	—	—	59.72	3.89	141*
	(a)	10Dq	fitted	37778	621	0.676	+278	0.736			
	(b)	10Dq	23449	fitted	579	0.631	-351	1.497			
	(c)	10Dq	23641	37649	602	0.656	± 159	0.547			
$[Cr(SCN)_4(C_5H_{15}N_3)]$	Expt.	17620	24000	38100	—	—	—	—	60.41	3.84	11.50**
	(a)	10Dq	fitted	38149	619	0.674	+49	0.128			
	(b)	10Dq	23929	fitted	611	0.665	-71	0.297			
	(c)	10Dq	23971	38129	616	0.671	± 29	0.098			
$K_2[Cr(NCS)_2(C_{14}H_{18}O_6N_4)]$	Expt.	18320	25500	38500	—	—	—	—	62.81	3.87	398*
	(a)	10Dq	fitted	40156	713	0.777	+1656	4.124			
	(b)	10Dq	23246	fitted	460	0.501	-2254	9.696			
	(c)	10Dq	24602	39388	602	0.656	± 898	2.965			

* Molar conductivity in water. Concentration $10^{-3} M$; ** Molar conductivity in acetone.

both second and third transitions are reproduced equally well. Again a possible misfit of ν_3 , which could be redistributed on ν_2 and ν_3 is not evident, if the method (c) is applied. However, if this were true the values of $\delta\nu$ (c) intermediate between $\delta\nu$ (a) and $\delta\nu$ (b) would be expected. But $\delta\nu$ (c) is always smaller than both $\delta\nu$ (a) and $\delta\nu$ (b) (Table 2). In the third complex, the deviation $\delta\nu$ (b) resulting from method (b), is extremely large, thus reflecting the uncertainty in the energy of the third band ν_3 . The values of 10Dq reveals that the ligand field strengths of different amines are in the order :

$DCTA > N-(2 \text{ aminoethyl})-1-3 \text{ propanediamine} > N-(2 \text{ aminoethyl})-1-2 \text{ ethanediamine.}$

The magnetic moment values observed are close to spin only value for octahedral complexes of chromium(III) (3.84-3.89BM). The values of molar conductances given in Table 2 indicate the presence of 2 and 4 ions in the case of complex nos. 1 and 3 respectively. The complex trithiocyanato (N-2 aminoethyl-1-3-propanediamine)-chromium(III) was found to be nonelectrolytic in nature as the value of molar conductance in acetone was 11.50 mhos. The reflectance spectra of the complexes gave nearly the same bands as were observed in their electronic spectra indicating thereby no dissociation of the complexes in solution.

The deviations $\delta\nu_{s,s}$ between the observed and calculated values (Table 2) also indicated an

octahedral geometry for these Cr(III) complexes. The spectrochemical series according to the nature of the ligand atom 'touching' the central ion is $I < Br < Cl < S < F < O < N < C$ and our series derived from Table 2, is, $N-(2 \text{ aminoethyl})-1-2 \text{ ethanediamine} < N-(2 \text{ aminoethyl})-1-3 \text{ propanediamine} < DCTA$. This order indicated the coordination of thiocyanate through N in the case of the complex of DCTA (10Dq is maximum). Nearly the same values, viz., 18350 cm^{-1} for $K_2[Cr(NCS)_4(\text{gly})]$, 18690 cm^{-1} for $K_2[Cr(NCS)_4(\text{ala})]$ and 18400 cm^{-1} for $K_2[Cr(NCS)_4(\text{CedtaH}_2)]$ are also reported in the literature. The mode of metal-thiocyanate bonding is dependent upon the metal itself, the nature of the other ligands in the coordination sphere and electronic and steric factors^{20,21}. The steric requirements for the angular M-S-CN linkage are more demanding than for linear M-N-CS bonding. Hence, a change to M-NCS bonding may occur when bulky ligands would create considerable steric strain.

IR Studies :

The shift in the frequencies of the three fundamental modes of vibrations in the thiocyanate ion upon complexing has been widely used to determine the bond type. The C-S stretching frequency has often been considered diagnostic of the metal bond since $\nu(CS)$ is at $690-720 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ for M-SCN and at $780-860 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ for M-NCS complexes. The CN stretching frequencies of a thiocyanate

TABLE 3—STRETCHING FREQUENCIES (cm^{-1}) OF THE IMPORTANT BANDS OF COORDINATED AMINES AND THIOCYANATE, DIFFERENCES FROM K SCN AND THE BOND TYPE*

Complexes**	Amines			Thiocyanate				Bond type
	$\nu\text{N-H}$	$\nu\text{O-N}$	νCOO^-	$\nu(\text{C-N})$	$\nu(\text{C-S})$	$\Delta\nu(\text{CN})$	$\Delta\nu(\text{C-S})$	
$\text{K}_2[\text{Cr}(\text{SCN})_6]$				2100(VS)	n.a.	+51	—	M-S
1	3240(S)	1590(S)		2110(VS)	720(w)	+61	-29	M-S
2	3200(m)	1205(m) 1580(m)	—	2109(VS)	740(w)	+60	-9	M-S
3	—	1140(w) 1000(w)	1660(S) 1400(S)	2060(VS)	800(m)	+11	+51	M-N

VS=Very strong, m=medium; w=weak

* The frequencies for KSCN are: $\nu(\text{CN})=2049$ and $\nu(\text{CS})=749 \text{ cm}^{-1}$

** See Table 1.

complex increase in the order: $\text{CNS} \langle \text{M-NCS} \rangle \langle \text{M-SCN} \rangle \langle \text{M-SCN-M}$. For M-SCN it is above 2100 cm^{-1} and for M-NCS, it is below or equal to 2100 cm^{-1} .²² In general $\nu(\text{CN})$ absorption is strong and exhibits a broad band for isothiocyanato and a sharp band for thiocyanate complexes.

According to Tramer²³ an increase in the frequency of $\nu(\text{CN})$ of $50-70 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ relative to free thiocyanato ions is indicative of M-SCN coordination. For M-NCS this increase is less than 40 cm^{-1} . A large increase of $70-120 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ is diagnostic of strong bridged complexes. For these cases in which it is possible to assign $\nu(\text{CS})$ frequencies, the differences from the free thiocyanate ion are: an increase of $40-90 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ for M-NCS and a decrease of $25-55 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ for M-SCN.

The $\nu(\text{CN})$, $\nu(\text{CS})$ and differences from KSCN and the types of bond formed in the case of our complexes are given in Table 3. When the thiocyanate group is N-bonded the $\nu(\text{CN})$ position is 2060 cm^{-1} and $\nu(\text{CS})$ is 800 cm^{-1} and when it is S-bonded, the $\nu(\text{CN})$ positions are 2100 , 2110 and 2109 cm^{-1} in the case of hexathiocyanato, N(2-aminoethyl) 1-2 ethanediamine and N(2-aminoethyl) 1-3 propanediamine respectively. The positions of $\nu(\text{CS})$ are 720 and 740 cm^{-1} in the case of N(2-aminoethyl) 1-2 ethanediamine and N(2-aminoethyl) 1-3 propanediamine respectively. Some of the most important bands of the organic ligands in the complexes and their assignments are also given in Table 3.

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